

EUPHEMISM AS AN ELEMENT OF ETHNOCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: The given article is dedicated to euphemisms in English language. The following tasks are planned to achieve the above mentioned aim: to give information about classification of euphemisms vocabulary, to collect information and data concerning euphemisms.

Key words: neologism, slang, cant, jargon vocabulary, literary vocabulary, standard English, non-literary) vocabulary, neutral words.

In the system of ethical culture, values are of special and high importance. They are related to the past of the people, the need and need for spiritual education when the problem of spirituality becomes more urgent, it is considered as an authoritative concept, a sacred factor that ensures the harmony of the past and the future, an invincible force in stabilizing the moral balance. The value category is considered in a strong line with the concepts of national freedom, liberty, freedom, immortal customs and traditions, and national identity, especially at the critical stages of national development. Things, events and events of great importance to society, nation and individual: freedom, goodness, equality, peace, truth, enlightenment, culture, material and spiritual wealth, monuments, beauty, moral

traits and qualities, traditions, customs, tradition, etc. make up the value system. Value is a broad and diverse concept, and its many aspects, such as philosophical, ethical, educational, linguistic, complicate description and interpretation. The diversity of the phenomenon causes imperfections in its explanation and interpretation. Ethnocultural values contribute to the preservation and protection of identity, survival from the danger of ethnic and national convergences and development on the basis of ethnic independence, ethnic consciousness and worldview serves to keep free from dependence. Ethnic values are the basis of ethnic collectivity. The ethnic group is genetic, occurs under the influence of socio-economic, natural-geographical factors. And this is a legitimate and objective process, based on self-awareness and differentiation from others will happen. Understanding the identity and the differences between this identity and others maturity lies at the core of any national or ethnic consciousness. Human consciousness and identity is an active subject who carries out

the process of understanding. Of course, consciousness brings awareness emits. The following points of SL Rubinstein are important: — Consciousness is self-awareness, a person is not born from "I", self-awareness is during the development of a person's consciousness, it appears only when it is formed as a real independent entity.

Ethnic identity is, regardless of our will, social consciousness as one of the forms, on the basis of contrasting features, character and images is formed. Different from each other. A type of relationship based on difference will come. It appears in such forms as nature and man, man and man, man and spirit. Cases of different perceptions of ethnic culture in the mirror of values is common [19;56].

In this sense, later scientists and political scientists among the peoples the uniqueness of the value of cultural-civilizational differences between nations and countries based on accumulated experience and conclusions about the cause of conflicts the main attention of the researchers to the conflict between ethnic groups, to the values that lead to their separation from each other, alienation, integration are looking at.

Conflicts between different ethnocultures in the mirror of individual values R. Benedict wrote in his time: "every culture, in others, it ignores, suppresses, and exists the fundamental consciousness produces things that are not. A culture with difficulty in the value of money for some, for others, they are the basis of everyday life and behavior. Technology even important spheres of life of a society are unprecedentedly weak in its aspects, extremely primitive, and in another, technological advances are complex and specific situations is very cleverly calculated. One society is youth, the other - of death, and the third is the huge cultural of life after death builds its superstructure.

Western scientists such as F. Barth and S. Huntington also want to divide nations

It is also valuable about the specific ethnic and civilizational values it brings expressed their opinions.

F. Barth defines the boundaries of ethnos and shows ethnic differences If we focus on the value of cultural values, the second one clearly defines the peoples shows certain cultural-civilizational values that distinguish it. And so, individualism, liberalism, rule of law, free market, etc. Western Europe,

A very important value for US Americans is Islam, to a certain extent for Confucianism, Pro-Slavic and other cultures characterized by alienation. It is known that separate, disconnected, separated from the system to see values as differentiators and determinants of a certain ethnoculture not enough. Euphemism is a universal linguistic phenomenon, its linguistic essence is crude, coarse, unspeakable concepts are softened and veiled in speech consists of expression. The function of units representing this phenomenon euphemisms do. Euphemisms with words, phraseology, word combinations can be expressed. Euphemisms in the language are originally

disease, various monsters, abnormal resulting from the ban on naming the forces. Later people categorize any notions that may harm themselves those who started The need to replace these concepts creates euphemisms in the language did By somewhat later periods of language development, it is rough and coarse other language units that meet the requirements of cultural communication - who started calling with euphemisms.

Euphemism in English and Uzbek with lexical and phraseological units emerges. In these languages, together with separate euphemistic units, euphemistic function words and phraseologisms that perform are also observed. English and Uzbek are domestic languages. There is a synonymy between the relationship of form and meaning of euphemisms. This euphemistic synonymy is purely lexical, purely phraseological and lexical-phraseological synonymy appears.

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